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CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN CHILDREN WITH VARIOUS FORMS OF ACUTE VIRAL HEPATITIS B

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In recent years, a significant decrease in the incidence of acute viral hepatitis has been observed in Uzbekistan. At the same time, a growing population of patients with chronic viral hepatitis continues to form, contributing to the further spread of infection. The wide spectrum of clinical manifestations of acute viral hepatitis B (AVHB), ranging from asymptomatic carriage to severe forms with rapid progression to chronic hepatitis or acute liver failure, is determined by several factors. Among these, molecular and genetic variants of the hepatitis B virus (HBV) occupy a leading position. Further investigation of the clinical course and the state of cellular immunity in children with AVHB remains highly relevant and represents a timely direction in modern hepatology.

Recent studies have demonstrated that the cellular component of the immune system, particularly T-helper cells, plays a crucial role in the induction of an effective antiviral immune response [1,2,5].

There are relatively few studies in the literature devoted to the investigation of clinical and immunological changes in infants and young children with AVHB.

Objective of the study: To investigate the pattern of changes in clinical and immunological parameters in young children with different forms of acute viral hepatitis B.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study included 96 pediatric patients with AVHB: 30 children with a mild form, 33 with a moderate form, and 33 with a severe form of the disease. All patients were hospitalized at the 4th City Children's Clinical Infectious Diseases Hospital and the 5th City Clinical Infectious Diseases Hospital in Tashkent. The control group consisted of 20 practically healthy children of comparable age.

Lymphocyte phenotyping was performed using monoclonal antibodies against CD3, CD4, CD8, CD16, and CD20 (Sorbet LLC, Moscow, Russian Federation). Serum concentrations of immunoglobulins A, M, and G were determined by radial immunodiffusion according to the Mancini method (1964) using monospecific antisera produced by the N.F. Gamaleya Research Institute of Epidemiology and Microbiology. Serum cytokine levels (IL-1 β , IL-4, and TNF- α) were measured using ELISA test systems manufactured by Cytokine LLC (St. Petersburg, Russia). The sensitivity of the assay ranged from 5 to 30 pg/mL.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The clinical and biochemical parameters of the examined pediatric patients corresponded to generally accepted diagnostic criteria and severity classifications for viral hepatitis. Severe forms of acute viral hepatitis B (AVHB) were characterized by more prolonged and pronounced manifestations of the main clinical syndromes, including intoxication, cholestasis, and cytolysis, compared to mild and moderate forms.

The development of acute liver failure (ALF) was associated with a significantly higher incidence of hemorrhagic syndrome (69.6%), with the most severe manifestation being gastrointestinal bleeding. In addition, patients with ALF exhibited qualitatively new symptoms of early intoxication, including signs of hepatic encephalopathy such as episodes of psychomotor agitation, altered consciousness, and subjective sensations described as "blackouts." A reduction in liver size during disease progression was documented in 39.1% of cases.

Increasing severity of AVHB was associated with elevated serum bilirubin levels and increased alanine aminotransferase (ALT) activity. Simultaneously, a decrease in prothrombin index and fibrinogen levels was observed. Total protein, albumin, and γ -globulin levels in patients with mild and moderate forms of AVHB remained within normal limits. In contrast, children with severe disease demonstrated a tendency toward decreased γ -globulin levels.

Mean hematological parameters did not significantly differ from normal values in most patient groups. However, children with severe AVHB and ALF showed a statistically significant decrease in hemoglobin levels and platelet counts, along with an increase in erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) during disease progression.

The results of immunological studies in young children with various forms of AVHB are presented in the table.

As shown in the table, severe forms of AVHB were characterized by a more pronounced decrease in the relative counts of T-lymphocytes and their main subpopulations (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+) in peripheral blood compared to non-severe forms. However, taking into account the lymphocytosis observed during the first three days of illness, the absolute values of lymphocyte subpopulations at the initial examination in this group did not differ significantly from those observed in patients with moderate disease.

At the same time, the immunoregulatory index (CD4+/CD8+) remained largely unchanged. The most pronounced decrease in immunocompetent cell counts in peripheral blood was observed in children with acute liver failure (ALF).

The absolute number of B-lymphocytes (CD20+) and natural killer (NK) cells (CD16+) in children with mild and moderate forms of AVHB did not differ significantly from the control group. However, in severe forms of the disease, a statistically significant increase in B-lymphocyte counts was observed, whereas NK-cell levels were reduced from the first days of illness.

The analysis of serum cytokine dynamics in children with different forms of AVHB revealed that disease severity was directly proportional to the concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and TNF- α). In mild and moderate forms of the disease, only moderate increases in serum IL-1 β and TNF- α levels were detected. In contrast, in severe forms, the concentrations of these cytokines were markedly elevated.

Repeated measurements demonstrated a decrease in cytokine levels in all patients, except those with severe disease, in whom cytokine concentrations remained persistently high.

Serum IL-4 levels at disease onset were only slightly elevated in children with mild and moderate forms. During the course of illness, IL-4 concentrations gradually increased. In severe forms, however, the opposite pattern was observed: maximal cytokine levels were detected at the initial examination, followed by lower levels during subsequent testing.

It is well established that monocytes and macrophages are the primary producers of cytokines [3,4,6]. Therefore, elevated serum concentrations of these mediators reflect increased functional activity of macrophages, directly correlating with the severity of acute viral hepatitis B. The highest serum levels of IL-1 β and TNF- α in children with severe disease may indicate the greatest degree of immune response activation in severe forms of AVHB in early childhood, as these cytokines are key inducers of both cellular and humoral immune responses.

1.

Table
Dynamics of Peripheral Blood Lymphocyte Subpopulation Counts and Serum Cytokine Concentrations in Young Children with Different Forms of Acute Viral Hepatitis B ($M \pm m$)

Parameters	Healthy Controls (n = 20)	Acute Viral Hepatitis B (AVHB)		
		Mild Form (n = 30)	Moderate Form (n = 33)	Severe Form (n = 33)
CD3 ⁺ , %	60,0±2,3	58,0±2,5	54,0±2,7	51,0±2,3
CD3 ⁺ , 10 ⁹ /л	3,22±0,14	3,2±0,11	3,1±0,17	2,8±0,09
CD4 ⁺ , %	27,0±2,7	25,0±1,9	23,0±1,4	21,0±0,15
CD4 ⁺ , 10 ⁹ /л	2,47±0,11	2,48±0,15	2,46±0,14	2,44±0,16
CD8 ⁺ , %	27,2±1,96	26,0±1,2	24,0±1,4	22,0±1,7
CD8 ⁺ , 10 ⁹ /л	2,47±0,11	2,4±0,16	2,39±0,15	2,30±0,11
CD16 ⁺ , %	17,0±2,2	16,0±2,1	14,0±2,0	12,0±1,9
CD16 ⁺ , 10 ⁹ /л	2,26±0,11	2,24±0,12	2,2±0,14	2,14±0,12
CD20 ⁺ , %	21,45±1,9	20,0±1,0	17,0±1,2	15,0±1,3
CD20 ⁺ , 10 ⁹ /л	2,36±0,4	2,3±0,3	2,25±0,11	2,18±0,12
IL-1β, пг/мл	40,0±2,1	60,0±5,0	100,0±4,8	120,0±5,2
IL-4, пг/мл	45,0±4,1	58,0±3,2	78,0±4,1	32,0±3,3
TNF-α, пг/мл	3,5±0,3	8,0±0,8	28,0±1,4	40,0±1,7

The analysis of humoral immunity parameters in children with different severities of acute viral hepatitis B (AVHB) during the course of the disease revealed an increase in serum concentrations of immunoglobulins M, G, and A. From the first days of the icteric period, a statistically significant elevation of IgM and IgA levels was observed in patients with moderate and severe forms of the disease. Moreover, this increase was more pronounced in severe cases.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, in young children with severe forms of AVHB, the following characteristics of the immune response were identified:

1. A significant decrease in the relative number of T-lymphocytes and their subpopulations in peripheral blood. The number of NK cells (CD16⁺) was reduced from the earliest days of the disease.
2. Disease severity was found to be directly proportional to the concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1β and TNF-α).

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